

СОЦІАЛЬНО-ТРУДОВІ ПРОБЛЕМИ

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Методи соціально-психологічної політики управління персоналом на підприємствах харчової промислової в умовах війни

Предметом дослідження є методи соціально-психологічної політики управління персоналом.

Метою дослідження є розгляд соціально-психологічних аспектів управління персоналом під тиском війни.

Методи дослідження. Для написання статті було використано загальнонаукові та спеціальні методи і прийоми наукового пізнання.

Результати роботи. У статті досліджено процес впливу соціально-психологічного управління на ефективність діяльності підприємств харчової промисловості в умовах війни. Наведений комплекс умов забезпечення соціально-психологічного захисту працівників підприємства. Проведено аналіз успішних кейсів соціально-психологічної політики, які застосовуються на Миронівському хлібопродукту, IDS Ukraine, Bayadera Group, ПРАТ «Лантманнен Акса».

Галузь застосування результатів. Менеджмент персоналу, економіка, харчова промисловість, управління та розвиток підприємств.

Висновки. Найкраще поєднання методів соціально-психологічної політики у харчовій промисловості під час війни – це симбіоз безпеки, комунікації, компенсацій та залучення до спільної місії. Ця політика має бути комплексною, тому що лише матеріальна підтримка без психологічної і навпаки не дає повного ефекту. Прозорість та справедливість у рішеннях керівництва формують головний психологічний ресурс – довіру персоналу. Мотивація через значущість праці стає потужним стабілізатором колективу. Необхідна гнучкість у роботі з кадрами, як умова виживання підприємств: адаптивність до ризиків дозволяє зберегти виробництво харчових продуктів й робочі місця.

Ключові слова: соціально-психологічні методи, управління персоналом, мотивація, страхування, підприємства, харчова промисловість, кейс, соціальні проекти, HR-інструменти.

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Methods of socio-psychological HR policy in food industry enterprises during wartime

The subject of the study is methods of social and psychological personnel management policy.

The purpose of the study is to examine the socio–psychological aspects of personnel management under the pressure of war.

Research methods. General scientific and special methods and techniques of scientific knowledge were used to write the article.

Results of the work. The article examines the process of the influence of social and psychological management on the effectiveness of food industry enterprises in wartime. A set of conditions for ensuring the social and psychological protection of enterprise employees is presented. An analysis of successful cases of social and psychological policy applied at Myronivsky Hliboproduct, IDS Ukraine, Bayadera Group, and PJSC Lantmannen Akxa is conducted.

Field of application of results. Personnel management, economics, food industry, enterprise management and development.

Conclusions. The best combination of social and psychological policy methods in the food industry during wartime is a symbiosis of security, communication, compensation and involvement in a common mission. This policy must be comprehensive, because material support without psychological support, and vice versa, does not have the full effect. Transparency and fairness in management decisions form the main psychological resource — staff trust. Motivation through the significance of work becomes a powerful stabilizer for the team. Flexibility in working with personnel is necessary as a condition for the survival of enterprises: adaptability to risks allows food production and jobs to be preserved.

Keywords: socio–psychological methods, personnel management, motivation, insurance, enterprises, food industry, case study, social projects, HR tools.

Problem statement. War and staff shortages have made it extremely important to develop and retain personnel in food industry enterprises. All of the company's personnel and social policies are viewed as a complex task, requiring adaptation to the new labour market, strengthening of social programmes, and attraction of talent. Due to the war, socio–psychological programmes are coming to the fore.

In the current economic climate, it is becoming increasingly important for companies to develop effective socio–psychological policies as a tool for ensuring the social protection of employees, as well as to choose rational models of socially responsible behaviour for management personnel.

Mature businesses are no longer looking for quick profits; they are creating long–term value. And this value is now inconceivable without responsibility towards people. Corporate culture, the ESG approach, and concern for well–being are not just buzzwords, but concrete actions that build the reputation of an employer's brand. And in this system, socio–psychological programmes play an important role, because there is a choice between temporary savings and long–term success, between costs and real investments.

Analysis of recent studies and publications. The following scholars have devoted their work to the issue of social and psychological poli-

cy in enterprises: T. Berezyanko, O. Cherep, S. Boi-da, O. Dragan, I. Fedulova, Y. Shiron, V. Yemtsov, G. Zakharchin, T. Polozova, T. Gurzhiy, T. Shterma, M. Manilich, S. Ostryanina, and others.

The purpose of the article is to study the impact of socio–psychological methods on the efficiency of food industry enterprises and to analyse the implementation of effective personnel management strategies during martial law.

Presentation of the main research material. The war has caused significant financial losses to the Ukrainian economy, especially in sectors such as industry, agriculture and infrastructure. At the same time, the conditions of high psychological pressure on entrepreneurs manifest themselves in stress, anxiety, burnout and decreased motivation. In this regard, entrepreneurs are forced to quickly adapt to new business conditions, change strategies, and look for new markets and sources of supply. State support, including financial assistance, tax breaks, and relocation programmes, has played an important role in preserving businesses. In addition, innovative solutions such as business digitalisation, transition to remote work and production of new products have enabled many enterprises to survive and develop [1, pp. 54–55].

Modern employee support is based on conditions where people can be motivated, productive and healthy at the same time. The war has radically

changed priorities, and fatigue and stress directly affect the safe performance of work. Constant air raid alerts, night-time sirens and hiding in shelters have a significant impact on employees' well-being. It is therefore very important to take their psychological and emotional state into account when planning work processes. Employers who devote a lot of time to this issue will maintain their leading positions in the Ukrainian food production market.

The main tasks of implementing the company's social and psychological policy are:

- to create a set of conditions to ensure the social and psychological protection of the company's employees;
- creating a positive image for society and all categories of employees;
- creating a favourable social and psychological climate;
- developing and implementing a system of benefits and guarantees for management personnel, aimed at motivating them to pursue self-development;
- improving the individual qualification level of management personnel;
- balancing the interests of management personnel and the entire company by agreeing on value guidelines for joint effective activities.

Social and psychological management of an enterprise is implemented through appropriate methods, which, in turn, affect both individual employees and the workforce as a whole, as well as the relationships between them. This creates a need for a comprehensive approach to developing a system of social and psychological management methods that takes into account both individual and group components. As a result, the enterprise's management will be able to make appropriate management decisions regarding the application of certain management methods in order to effectively motivate employees, increase their productivity and form an organisational culture [1, p. 17].

In our opinion, a socially responsible enterprise should actively develop the following areas:

- care for employees;
- charity;
- volunteering;
- environmental initiatives.

Food industry enterprises are obliged to create a working environment where people feel protected, confident, comfortable and motivated despite the constant stress and fatigue.

The most valuable and essential benefits for food industry employees are medical insurance, psychological support, and life insurance. In our opinion, insurance is not only financial compensation for risks, but also a tool for reducing anxiety, increasing employees' sense of security, investing in personnel, the company's reputation, and sustainable development, rather than an additional expense.

In times of war and instability, the socio-psychological function of insurance programmes becomes paramount. Insurance programmes often cover medical expenses in cases where a person has been injured as a result of shelling while outside the combat zone or occupation zone. This means that even in extreme circumstances, employees can count on support: from organising treatment to full reimbursement of medical expenses.

Insurance is also a motivational tool that provides tangible benefits without requiring a direct increase in salary. It not only reduces the financial burden on the employee at the moment, but also guarantees them financial and psychological security. If an employer chooses medical insurance and accident insurance, this enhances the social protection of the employee. This includes not only medical assistance in case of illness, but also financial support in critical situations such as injury, loss of working capacity or even death. For the employee, this means confidence that their family will not be left without support.

Food industry companies need a comprehensive approach (medical insurance plus accident coverage). Staff insurance is an investment in the employer's brand. The stronger the company's social policy, the more attractive it is to future employees and partners.

To improve the social policy of food industry companies, we recommend including insurance in the corporate social package, building a differentiated system (basic coverage + additional options of your choice), using group contracts (cheaper than individual ones), regularly conduct staff surveys on satisfaction with insurance programmes, ensure transparent communication: what risks are covered, how to act in the event of an insured event.

The main indicators of effective social and psychological policy will be a reduction in staff turnover, a decrease in absenteeism and sick leave, an increase in eNPS (employee loyalty index), and a reduction in conflicts. Thus, insurance becomes

not only a financial but also a psychological stabiliser for staff. It maintains trust, reduces stress levels and helps food industry enterprises maintain productivity even in wartime.

Psycho-emotional state is directly related to productivity: when an employee is in a state of chronic anxiety or emotional exhaustion, it affects their ability to make decisions. According to the findings of Gradus Research, which conducts annual national mental health surveys in Ukraine, companies that ignore the mental well-being of their employees have a higher risk of staff turnover and deterioration in the quality of teamwork.

Let's take a closer look at some examples of social and psychological policies implemented in food industry enterprises. Let's take the experience of MHP, an international food and agrotechnology company and producer of high-quality food products. For Myronivsky Hliboproduct, caring for employees has become a strategic decision and a key competitive advantage. This company has created a powerful ecosystem of care and is developing the OHS (Occupational Health and Safety) vector. It combines five strategic areas: health care, occupational safety, civil protection, fire safety, and traffic safety.

After the pandemic, staff safety and health have become a business necessity for MHP, which is why the company has its own corporate medical centre. The specialists at this centre have interdisciplinary expertise in occupational pathology – they understand the specifics of production and know how working conditions affect the physical condition of workers. They combine the functions of a family doctor, an expert in occupational diseases and a trusted doctor for insurance companies. They can also motivate employees to lead a healthy lifestyle, engage in prevention and treatment, and understand production risks. According to the results of the latest internal MHP survey, 98% of employees are proud to be part of a powerful agro-industrial holding team.

IDS Ukraine is represented in Ukraine by the Morshynska, Myrhorodska, and Aqua Life brands and has over 2,000 employees. Employee support is one of the priority programmes for the mineral water producer. In addition to voluntary medical insurance, the company pays for employee treatment that is not covered by insurance. In total, the company spends about UAH 15 million annually on healthcare. The company has also introduced a fi-

nancial assistance tool that is provided for various cases, including compensation for the medical expenses of employees or their family members (up to 75% of the costs). There is a separate fund to support employees whose property has been damaged as a result of the war (up to UAH 100,000). The amount of such assistance in 2023 reached about UAH 3 million. The company has a three-year housing compensation programme for specialists from other localities. Employees who reach the performance threshold are eligible for an annual salary indexation of 15% on average, depending on the personnel category.

Today, IDS Ukraine has a whole department dedicated to providing psychological support to employees, which was established during the coronavirus pandemic. All employees have access to psychological support 24/7. In more complex cases, specialists are involved through the medical insurance programme. The corporate limit covers the option of a personal psychologist. A separate area is the company's organisation of meditation, yoga, and other classes for employees.

In addition, key challenges for the company's HR function have already become, and will intensify in the future, issues of retaining people, attracting new employees (against the backdrop of a growing shortage of personnel in the market), and supporting mental health.

Three years of full-scale war have radically changed the labour market. Companies are finding new solutions, creating jobs, organising training, and developing and implementing policies for the reintegration of veterans. Employers are creating a special microclimate in the workplace, helping mobilised employees, organising large charitable projects, paying taxes regularly, and implementing new business approaches. Difficult conditions and limited opportunities force us to work efficiently and become better.

Another example of a successful case of socially responsible policy implementation is Bayadera Group. As of 2025, the company has more than 30 own brands, including such well-known vodka brands as HLIBNY DAR, Kozatska Rada, Persha Hildiya; Koblevo wines and cognacs, Marengo vermouths and sparkling wines, etc. Since 2009, the company has been the undisputed leader in the vodka category, with a 35% share of the domestic market. In addition, the company is the exclusive importer of well-known global brands. Finan-

cial assistance to the Ukrainian army during the war amounts to 85 million hryvnia (as of January 2025).

Bayadera Group has joined the organisation of an educational project for students called «Defence of Ukraine». Its main task is to foster a sense of patriotism, love for the Motherland, and respect for defenders among the younger generation.

Currently, the holding employs 3,500 people, and about 40 new vacancies appear every month. But the company is not only looking for new employees, it is also updating programmes to retain its existing team. One such programme is relocation assistance. Employees from frontline or occupied territories are encouraged to move to safer cities where the holding company has branches. Additional bonuses include one-time financial compensation for employees who have lost their homes as a result of Russian attacks, as well as assistance for those who have gone to the front and their families. The company has a successful «Internal Trainer» programme, in which experienced employees share their expertise with other colleagues[6] .

Another example of systematic organisation of social and psychological work is PJSC Lantmannen Aksa. The company produces food products in accordance with high European quality standards and Ukrainian raw materials in the city of Boryspil. PJSC Lantmannen AXA actively supports social initiatives and engages in charity work, regularly donating dry breakfasts, porridge, bars and snacks to charitable organisations, children's institutions, hospitals, volunteer centres and the Armed Forces of Ukraine and the Defence Forces.

Supporting employee morale during wartime has become one of the most important tasks for HR directors. In conditions of constant danger and stress, companies are developing comprehensive programmes that include various aspects of psychological support. Direct and regular communication between management and employees plays an important role, allowing for quick responses to problems and maintaining a high level of trust, which helps to create an atmosphere of support and confidence among employees.

For food industry enterprises, an important element is the implementation of resilience and well-being programmes that teach employees methods of self-organisation and emotional self-regulation, allow for regular monitoring of employees' con-

dition, and are aimed at reducing stress and increasing emotional resilience. This allows them to better adapt to stressful situations and maintain their working capacity. Along with this, we suggest developing programmes that provide financial support. All this creates conditions for maintaining a high level of employee motivation and productivity, even in such difficult circumstances.

The following methods are used in the research process: logical generalisation – to systematise the results regarding the impact of social activities on increasing business profitability; systematic analysis – to group social projects; comparative analysis – to study the dynamics of costs for the implementation of social programmes; correlation analysis – to identify priority social projects for the enterprise; mathematical modelling – to study the impact of social investments on financial and economic performance indicators[3, p. 266].

Artificial intelligence is becoming an increasingly popular tool in HR practice and is gradually being integrated into the HR practices of Ukrainian companies, as it allows for the automation of many routine processes. Some food industry companies are already actively using AI-based systems to select candidates for vacancies, although some companies are still in the process of studying AI functionality and have not yet implemented its use. These systems are capable of analysing large amounts of data, including CVs, cover letters and social media profiles, to quickly find the most suitable candidates – this approach significantly reduces recruitment time.

Modern HR specialists in Ukraine face numerous challenges that complicate their work and require a constant search for new solutions. One of the main problems is the shortage of personnel caused by mass mobilisation and migration of the working-age population, which has resulted in the complexity of HR specialists' work in wartime conditions. Many qualified specialists have left the country, leading to a shortage of personnel. This is forcing HR directors to review their recruitment strategies: searching among internally displaced persons, retraining existing employees, and attracting older workers.

Conclusions

Therefore, based on the research conducted, we would like to emphasise that employees expect the company to protect their lives and health: shelter, an algorithm of actions during emergencies, med-

ical and psychological support. Without creating a sense of security, any other HR tools lose their effectiveness. In a crisis, transparency and honesty on the part of management reduce panic and rumours. Employees need regular briefings, feedback channels and explanations of strategic decisions. Trust directly affects productivity and team cohesion.

Food industry companies need to implement stress management training and provide access to psychologists/coaches and support groups. Flexible schedules, the possibility of short vacations or rotations reduce the risk of burnout.

In life-threatening situations, employees expect clear and fair payment rules (bonuses, insurance, premiums). Social packages (insurance, support for IDP or military families) increase loyalty and reduce anxiety.

The implementation of staff social development programmes as a priority area for corporate social responsibility demonstrates a systematic approach to the formation of an effective enterprise management strategy that ensures its competitiveness, innovative development, long-term sustainability, high image and positive social role.

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